

SILICE: A Spanish proposal for a local scholarly information system based only on open data

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Intro

- Bibliometric indicators supplied by commercial platforms
 - Because they require a great economic effort
 - This causes lack of independence in evaluation processes
- New advances:
 - In the automatic extraction of citations (academic search engines)
 - In the releasing of Open sources (Crossref, OpenAlex, COCI)
- Explore the possibilities and limitations of bibliographic databases ingested by open data.
 - Creation of new and *ad hoc* scientific information services

SILICE (Sistema de información para la Literatura Científica Española)

A beta web application (web site) that attempts to gather the scholarly production:

Researchers

+

Organizations

System is structured in several relational modules that illustrate the outputs and associated metrics of each entity.

Data Structure

1

2

3

4

5

6

Author

The screenshot shows the SILICE search results page. On the left, there are filters for 'Disciplina' (Social Sciences & Humanities, Applied Psychology, Clinic Psychology) and 'Afilación' (Universidad de Córdoba, Universidad de Granada, CSIC). The main area is titled 'Resultados' and shows three author entries:

Author	Institution	Citas	Altimétricas
José Luis Ortega	Instituto de Estudios Sociales Avanzados, CSIC #Social Sciences & Humanities	501	224
José Ortega	Universidad de Granada #Applied Psychology #Clinic Psychology	50	22
Luis Ortega	Universidad de Granada #Education #Archeology	1	0

At the bottom of the page, there are logos for the Spanish Government, CSIC, and IESA, along with project information: 'Proyecto financiado por Plan Nacional de Investigación, Agencia Estatal de Investigación, Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación, PID2019-106510GB-I00'. A footer link says 'Ayuda | Quiénes | Sobre SILICE'.

Spanish authors selected from:

- ORCID: principal source (<100k)
- Including current affiliation
- Publications (Works)

In case of authors without ORCID

Claimed and editable profiles

Registered users include info and publications

Publications

Publications from authors \neq Publications from organizations

Mobility changes the affiliation (i.e. Microsoft Academic)

From authors

- To use Orcid to extract identifiers works.

From organization

- Organization search
 - Affiliation search
 - Crossref
 - OpenAlex

Metrics

Show the global impact of the publications, and not limited to the Spanish environment.

Only citations to Spanish papers.

Citations

- To build this citation database we attempt to use COCI and OpenAlex as main citation sources.

Altmetrics

- Crossref Event Data and Altmetric would be used to add altmetric mentions.

We aim to create a graph database (Neo4j) of citations where citation relationships are deposited.

Organizations

ROR

GRID

- First-level organizations
- Normalized with RoR

silice

Organización

Universidad de Granada

Multidisciplinary Life Sciences Physical Sciences
Social Sciences & Humanities Health Sciences +

18745 publicaciones 25047 citas

Publicaciones

Comparing university rankings
I Aguillo, J Bar-Ilan, M Levene, J Ortega
Scientometrics 85 (1), 243-256

Webometric ranking of world universities: Introduction, methodology...
IF Aguillo, B Granadino, JL Ortega, JA Prieto
Higher education in Europe 33 (2-3), 233-244

Scientific research activity and communication measured with ...
IF Aguillo, B Granadino, JL Ortega, JA Prieto
Journal of the American Society for information science and technology 57

Relationship between altmetric and bibliometric indicators across ...
JL Ortega
Journal of informetrics 9 (1), 39-49

Indicators for a webometric ranking of open access repositories

Autores

I Aguillo
35 publicaciones
65 citas

B Granadino
87 publicaciones
207 citas

JL Ortega
123 publicaciones
501 citas

JA Prieto
6 publicaciones
8 citas

M Fernández

GOBIERNO DE ESPAÑA MINISTERIO DE CIENCIA E INNOVACIÓN CSIC IESA Instituto de Estudios Sociales Avanzados
Proyecto financiado por Plan Nacional de Investigación, Agencia Estatal de Investigación, Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación. PID2019-106510GB-I00

Ayuda Oulenes Sobre SILICE

Discipline

- Disciplines assigned to articles through Scimago Journal Rank
 - Limited to journal articles

The screenshot displays the SILICE interface for the discipline 'Social Sciences & Humanities'. It features a horizontal bar chart of sub-disciplines, a list of publications, and a list of authors.

Disciplina
Social Sciences & Humanities

Sub-disciplines: Social Sciences, Archeology, Development, Education, Geography, Planning and Development, Health (social science), Law, Human Factors and Ergonomics, Library and Information Sciences, +

57401 publicaciones | **22421 citas**

Publicaciones

- Comparing university rankings
I Aguillo, J Bar-Ilan, M Levene, J Ortega
Scientometrics 85 (1), 243-256
- Webometric ranking of world universities: Introduction, methodology...
IF Aguillo, B Granadino, JL Ortega, JA Prieto
Higher education in Europe 33 (2-3), 233-244
- Scientific research activity and communication measured with ...
IF Aguillo, B Granadino, JL Ortega, JA Prieto
Journal of the American Society for information science and technology 57
- Relationship between altmetric and bibliometric indicators across ...
JL Ortega
Journal of informetrics 9 (1), 39-49
- Disciplinary differences in the use of academic social networking sites

Organizaciones

- Universidad de Granada
- Universidad de Córdoba
- Instituto de Estudios Avanzados
- Universidad Politécnica de Valencia
- Universidad Complutense de Madrid
- Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona

Autores

- I Aguillo
35 publicaciones
65 citas
- B Granadino
87 publicaciones
207 citas
- JA Prieto
6 publicaciones
8 citas
- M Fernández
74 publicaciones
54 citas
- A Utrilla

Footer: GOBIERNO DE ESPAÑA, MINISTERIO DE CIENCIA E INNOVACIÓN, CSIC (CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS), IESA (Instituto de Estudios Sociales Avanzados), Proyecto financiado por Plan Nacional de Investigación, Agencia Estatal de Investigación, Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación. PID2019-106510GB-I00. Ayuda Quiénes Sobre SILICE.

Conclusion

- The first local information system with computed metrics
 - Much more reduced costs
 - Independent from commercial interests
- Based only on open sources
 - Customizable product
- Citations are independent from the publications database
 - Reducing space
 - Improving and accelerating the metrics computation

Grazie

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